

Development of Kifilideen's Rule to Solve Multiplication of Bi-Indexes, Tri-Indexes and n -Indexes Simultaneous Equations of Two Variables, Three Variables and n Variables Respectively

Kifilideen L. Osanyinpeju*

Department of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering, Bells University, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria (*amkifilideenosanyinpeju@gmail.com, kosanyinpeju@bellsuniversity.edu.ng; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8995-7559>).

ABSTRACT

Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms generates multiplication of tri- indexes or bi – indexes simultaneous equations of its components' migration level value, migration step value, and first term. There is a need to develop a simple, short, effective, and standardized rule or model to tackle such a problem. This study develops Kifilideen's Rule to solve the multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes, and n -indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables, and variables respectively. Elimination method, laws of indices, and cofactor and determinant of matrix were deployed in establishing, formulating, and modeling the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables, respectively. The Kifilideen's Rule was implemented in the form of a model in solving problems involving multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables, respectively. The general solution to solve the multiplication of index simultaneous equations of variables using Kifilideen's rule was inaugurated. The Kifilideen's Rule is in the form of a model to solve multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables, respectively, which was found to be effective, straightforward, reliable, interesting, easy, and intuitive to understand for students and beginners.

Keywords: Kifilideen's Rule, Simultaneous Equations, Multiplication of Bi-Indexes, Multiplication of Tri-Indexes, Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of simultaneous equations, also known as systems of linear equations, has a rich history with contributions from ancient civilizations and mathematicians which involve finding solutions for multiple equations with multiple variables, dates back thousands of years and spans various cultures (Grcar, 2011a; Khushbu and Poonia, 2021). The earliest known evidence of solving simultaneous equations dates back to ancient Babylonian mathematicians where clay tablets showed solutions to systems of linear equations. They used algebraic methods to solve systems of linear equations, often in the context of practical problems, such as determining the dimensions of fields or distribution of goods (Zara, 2008). The Babylonians utilized geometric

Momona Ethiopian Journal of Science (MEJS), V17(2):302-323,2025 ©CNCS, Mekelle University,ISSN:2220-184X

Submitted: 3rd September 2024

Accepted: 1st October 2024

Published: 15th December 2025

© CNCS Mekelle University. This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. This license enables re-users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator. The license allows for commercial use. To view the details of this license, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. CC: Creative Commons; BY: credit must be given to the creator.

methods and tables to solve linear and quadratic equations, including systems involving two equations (Burton, 2011).

In ancient Egypt (1650 BCE), the Rhind Papyrus contained problems that involved solving systems of linear equations (Fribera, 2008). The ancient Greeks, particularly Diophantus (fl. 3rd century CE), made significant contributions to the field of algebra, including solving simultaneous equations (Rizos and Gkrekas, 2022). Diophantus of Alexandria contributed to the development of algebraic methods. Though Diophantus primarily dealt with single-variable equations, his work laid the groundwork for future developments in algebra (Sfard, 1995). During the Middle Ages, Arabic mathematicians such as Al-Khwarizmi (780-850 CE) and Al-Kindi (801-873 CE) made significant contributions to algebra, including solving simultaneous equations (Rahaman, 2022).

Islamic mathematicians such as Al-Khwarizmi and Omar Khayyam expanded on Greek and Indian mathematics, further developing methods for solving equations (Baki, 1992). While their work primarily focused on quadratic equations, their contributions to algebra helped set the stage for later developments in simultaneous equations (Kabar, 2023). Al-Khwarizmi's book "Al-Kitab al-mukhtasar fi hisab al-jabrwa'l-muqabala" (The Compendious Book on Calculation by Completion and Balancing) introduced algebraic methods for solving linear and quadratic equations, including simultaneous equations. In the 16th century, Italian mathematician Girolamo Cardano (1501-1576) developed methods for solving systems of linear equations (Heffer and Rothman, 2014). René Descartes (1596-1650) introduced the concept of coordinates and graphing, which laid the foundation for modern methods of solving simultaneous equations (Neovius, 2013). René Descartes and Pierre de Fermat were pivotal figures in the development of analytical geometry, which links algebra and geometry (Oaks, 2021). Descartes' work on Cartesian coordinates provided a geometric interpretation of simultaneous equations, allowing for the visualization of solutions as points of intersection between curves or lines (Neovius, 2013).

In the 18th century, Swiss mathematician Leonhard Euler (1707-1783) developed the method of substitution for solving systems of linear equations (Carmin, 2021). In the 19th century, German mathematician Carl Friedrich Gauss (1777-1855) developed the method of elimination for solving systems of linear equations, which is still widely used today (Grcar, 2011a). The 20th century saw the development of matrix theory and the introduction of the concept of linear independence, which further advanced the solution of simultaneous equations (Grcar, 2011b).

Today, simultaneous equations are an essential tool in various fields, including physics, engineering, economics, and computer science, and are solved using a variety of methods,

including Cramer's rule, Gaussian elimination, Jacobian method, Gauss-Seidel method, LU decomposition, and matrix inversion (Samuel, 2011; Woollard, 2015; Osanyinpeju, 2024a). Key figures in the history of simultaneous equations include Diophantus (fl. 3rd century CE), Al-Khwarizmi (780-850 CE), Girolamo Cardano (1501-1576), René Descartes (1596-1650), Leonhard Euler (1707-1783) and Carl Friedrich Gauss (1777-1855). These mathematicians, along with many others, have contributed to the development of methods for solving simultaneous equations, which has had a profound impact on various fields of science and engineering.

Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms generates multiplication of tri – indexes or bi – indexes simultaneous equations of its components migration level value, k , migration step value, i , and first term, f . The Kifilideen's General Term Formula of the Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms is of the form:

$$T_n = k^a i^{n-m} f, \quad (1)$$

Where, T_n is the n^{th} term, k is the migration level value, i is the migration step value and f is the first term of the Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms (Osanyinpeju, 2021; Osanyinpeju, 2024b).

The Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms is the geometric versions of the Kifilideen's Arithmetic Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms (Osanyinpeju, 2022; Osanyinpeju, 2023). The Kifilideen's Arithmetic Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite and finite terms are originated and generalized from Kifilideen's Trinomial Theorem of infinite and finite terms respectively (Osanyinpeju, 2020a; Osanyinpeju, 2020b). There is need to develop a simple, short, effective and standardized rule, method or model to tackle multiplication of tri – indexes or bi – indexes simultaneous equations generated from Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite terms. Such developed model can be applied to solve mathematical or World problems which have the same pattern or form as the Kifilideen's Geometric Matrix Progression Sequence of infinite terms. With reference to method to solve multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes and n -indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables and n variables respectively, there is no available study. This study develops Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes and n -indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables and n variables respectively.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Elimination method, laws of indices, and cofactor and determinant of matrix were deployed in establishing, formulating and modelling the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables respectively.

2.1. Establishment of Kifilideen's Rule to Solve Multiplication of Bi-Indexes Simultaneous Equations of Two Variables

For a given multiplication of bi-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, say a and b such that:

$$a^x b^y = m, \quad (2)$$

$$a^w b^v = n, \quad (3)$$

The generation of the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables is illustrated as follow:

From (2) and (3), I have:

$$a^{\frac{x}{y}} b = m^{\frac{1}{y}}, \quad (4)$$

$$a^{\frac{w}{v}} b = n^{\frac{1}{v}}, \quad (5)$$

To find a , eliminate b by dividing (4) with (5),

$$a^{\frac{x}{y} - \frac{w}{v}} = m^{\frac{1}{y}} n^{-\frac{1}{v}},$$

$$a^{\frac{xv-wy}{yv}} = m^{\frac{1}{y}} n^{-\frac{1}{v}},$$

$$a = m^{\frac{1}{y} \left(\frac{yv}{xv-wy} \right)} n^{-\frac{1}{v} \left(\frac{yv}{xv-wy} \right)},$$

$$a = m^{\left(\frac{v}{xv-wy} \right)} n^{\left(\frac{-y}{xv-wy} \right)}, \quad (6)$$

From (2) and (3), I have:

$$ab^{\frac{y}{x}} = m^{\frac{1}{x}}, \quad (7)$$

$$ab^{\frac{v}{w}} = n^{\frac{1}{w}}, \quad (8)$$

To find b , eliminate a by dividing (7) with (8),

$$b^{\frac{y}{x} - \frac{v}{w}} = m^{\frac{1}{x}} n^{-\frac{1}{w}}, \quad b^{\frac{yw-vx}{xw}} = m^{\frac{1}{x}} n^{-\frac{1}{w}}, \quad b = m^{\frac{1}{x} \left(\frac{xw}{yw-vx} \right)} n^{-\frac{1}{w} \left(\frac{xw}{yw-vx} \right)}, \quad b = m^{\left(\frac{w}{yw-vx} \right)} n^{\left(\frac{-x}{yw-vx} \right)},$$

$$b = m^{\left(\frac{-w}{vx-yw} \right)} n^{\left(\frac{x}{vx-yw} \right)}, \quad (9)$$

From (2) and (3), the determinant of matrix of the input index system is represented as Δ_{kif} and is given as:

$$\Delta_{kif} = \begin{vmatrix} x & y \\ w & v \end{vmatrix} = xv - wy, \quad (10)$$

Also, let the matrix of the input index system represent kif , so I have:

$$kif = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ w & v \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} \end{pmatrix},$$

The components of the cofactor of kif are given as:

$$kif_{11} = \text{cofactor of } d_{11} = v, \quad (11)$$

$$kif_{12} = \text{cofactor of } d_{12} = -w, \quad (12)$$

$$kif_{21} = \text{cofactor of } d_{21} = -y, \quad (13)$$

$$kif_{22} = \text{cofactor of } d_{22} = x, \quad (14)$$

Inputting (10), (11), (12), (13), and (14) in (6), I have:

$$a = m^{\left(\frac{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} n^{\left(\frac{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)},$$

Inputting (10), (11), (12), (13), and (14) in (9), I have:

$$b = m^{\left(\frac{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} n^{\left(\frac{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)},$$

Generally, the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, say a and b such that:

$$a^x b^y = m, \quad a^w b^v = n \quad \text{is given as:}$$

$$a = m^{\left(\frac{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} n^{\left(\frac{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)}, \quad (15)$$

$$b = m^{\left(\frac{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} n^{\left(\frac{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)}, \quad (16)$$

2.2. Inauguration of Kifilideen's Rule to Solve Multiplication of Tri-Indexes Simultaneous Equations of Three Variables

For a given multiplication of tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, say a, b and c such that:

$$a^e b^f c^g = m, \quad (17)$$

$$a^r b^s c^t = n, \quad (18)$$

$$a^x b^y c^z = p, \quad (19)$$

The generation of the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of tri-indexes simultaneous equations of three variables is illustrated below.

From (17), I have:

$$a^{\frac{e}{g}} b^{\frac{f}{g}} c = m^{\frac{1}{g}}, \quad (20)$$

From (18), I have:

$$a^{\frac{r}{t}} b^{\frac{s}{t}} c = n^{\frac{1}{t}}, \quad (21)$$

And from (19), I have:

$$a^{\frac{x}{z}} b^{\frac{y}{z}} c = p^{\frac{1}{z}}, \quad (22)$$

To eliminate c , divide (20) with (21) and (21) with (22), so we have: Dividing (20) with (21), so I have $a^{\frac{e-r}{gt}} b^{\frac{f-s}{gt}} = m^{\frac{1}{g}} n^{-\frac{1}{t}}$,

$$a^{\frac{et-gr}{gt}} b^{\frac{ft-gs}{gt}} = m^{\frac{1}{g}} n^{-\frac{1}{t}}, \quad (23)$$

$$a^{\frac{et-gr}{ft-gs}} b = m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{-\frac{g}{ft-gs}}, \quad (24)$$

Dividing (21) with (22), so I have $a^{\frac{r-x}{tz}} b^{\frac{s-y}{tz}} = n^{\frac{1}{t}} p^{-\frac{1}{z}}$,

$$a^{\frac{rz-tx}{tz}} b^{\frac{sz-yt}{tz}} = n^{\frac{1}{t}} p^{-\frac{1}{z}}, \quad (25)$$

$$a^{\frac{rz-tx}{sz-yt}} b = n^{\frac{z}{sz-yt}} p^{-\frac{t}{sz-yt}}, \quad (26)$$

To find a , eliminate b by dividing (24) with (26), so I have:

$$\frac{a^{\frac{et-gr}{ft-gs}} b^{\frac{rz-tx}{sz-yt}}}{a^{\frac{et-gr}{ft-gs}} b} = \frac{m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{-\frac{g}{ft-gs}} p^{-\frac{t}{sz-yt}}}{n^{\frac{z}{sz-yt}} p^{-\frac{t}{sz-yt}}},$$

$$a^{\frac{(et-gr)(sz-yt)-(rz-tx)(ft-gs)}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} = m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{\frac{-g(sz-yt)-z(ft-gs)}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} p^{\frac{t}{sz-yt}},$$

$$a^{\frac{etsz-et^2y-grsz+grty-(rztf-rzgs-xt^2f+txgs)}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} = m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{\frac{-gsz+gty-zft+zgs}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} p^{\frac{t}{sz-yt}},$$

$$a^{\frac{etsz-et^2y-grsz+grty-rztf+rzgs+xt^2f-txgs}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} = m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{\frac{gty-zft}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} p^{\frac{t}{sz-yt}},$$

$$a^{\frac{etsz-et^2y+grty-rztf+xt^2f-txgs}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} = m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{\frac{t(gy-zf)}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} p^{\frac{t}{sz-yt}},$$

$$a^{\frac{t(esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs)}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} = m^{\frac{t}{ft-gs}} n^{\frac{t(gy-zf)}{(ft-gs)(sz-yt)}} p^{\frac{t}{sz-yt}},$$

$$a^{esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs} = m^{sz-yt} n^{gy-zf} p^{ft-gs},$$

$$a^{esz-ety-fsr+xtf+gry-xgs} = m^{sz-yt} n^{gy-zf} p^{ft-gs}, \quad (27)$$

From (17), (18), and (19), the determinant of matrix of the input index system is represented as Δ_{kif} and is given as:

$$\Delta_{kif} = \begin{vmatrix} e & f & g \\ r & s & t \\ x & y & z \end{vmatrix} \quad (28a)$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = e \begin{vmatrix} s & t \\ y & z \end{vmatrix} - f \begin{vmatrix} r & t \\ x & z \end{vmatrix} + g \begin{vmatrix} r & s \\ x & y \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = e(sz - yt) - f(rz - xt) + g(ry - sx),$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = esz - eyt - fzt + fxt + gry - gxs, \quad (28b)$$

Also, let the matrix of the input index system represent kif , so I have:

$$kif = \begin{pmatrix} e & f & g \\ r & s & t \\ x & y & z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} d_{11} & d_{12} & d_{13} \\ d_{21} & d_{22} & d_{23} \\ d_{31} & d_{32} & d_{33} \end{pmatrix},$$

The components of the cofactor of kif are given as:

$$kif_{11} = \text{cofactor of } d_{11} = \begin{vmatrix} s & t \\ y & z \end{vmatrix} = sz - ty, \quad (29)$$

$$kif_{12} = \text{cofactor of } d_{12} = - \begin{vmatrix} r & t \\ x & z \end{vmatrix} = -(rz - xt) = xt - rz, \quad (30)$$

$$kif_{13} = \text{cofactor of } d_{13} = \begin{vmatrix} r & s \\ x & y \end{vmatrix} = ry - sx, \quad (31)$$

$$kif_{21} = \text{cofactor of } d_{21} = - \begin{vmatrix} f & g \\ y & z \end{vmatrix} = -(fz - gy) = gy - fz, \quad (32)$$

$$kif_{22} = \text{cofactor of } d_{22} = \begin{vmatrix} e & g \\ x & z \end{vmatrix} = ez - gx, \quad (33)$$

$$kif_{23} = \text{cofactor of } d_{23} = - \begin{vmatrix} e & f \\ x & y \end{vmatrix} = -(ey - fx) = fx - ey, \quad (34)$$

$$kif_{31} = \text{cofactor of } d_{31} = \begin{vmatrix} f & g \\ s & t \end{vmatrix} = ft - gs, \quad (35)$$

$$kif_{32} = \text{cofactor of } d_{32} = - \begin{vmatrix} e & g \\ r & t \end{vmatrix} = -(et - rg) = rg - et, \quad (36)$$

$$kif_{33} = \text{cofactor of } d_{33} = \begin{vmatrix} e & f \\ r & s \end{vmatrix} = es - fr, \quad (37)$$

Inputting (28), (29), (30), (31), (32), (33), (34), (35), (36), and (37) in (27), I have:

$$a^{\Delta_{kif}} = m^{kif_{11}} n^{kif_{21}} p^{kif_{31}},$$

$$a = m^{\left(\frac{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} n^{\left(\frac{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} p^{\left(\frac{kif_{31}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)}, \quad (36)$$

From (23), I have:

$$a^{\frac{et-gr}{gt}} b^{\frac{ft-gs}{gt}} = m^{\frac{1}{g}} n^{\frac{1}{t}}, \tag{23}$$

$$ab^{et-gr} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{g}{et-gr}}, \tag{37}$$

From (25), I have:

$$a^{\frac{rz-tx}{tz}} b^{\frac{sz-yt}{tz}} = n^{\frac{1}{t}} p^{\frac{1}{z}}, \tag{25}$$

$$ab^{rz-tx} = n^{\frac{z}{rz-tx}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}}, \tag{38}$$

To find b , I eliminate a by dividing (37) with (38), so I have:

$$b^{\frac{ft-gs}{et-gr} \frac{sz-yt}{rz-tx}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{g}{et-gr} \frac{z}{rz-tx}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{\frac{(ft-gs)(rz-tx)-(et-gr)(sz-yt)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{-g(rz-tx)-z(et-gr)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{\frac{ftr-ft^2x-gsrz+gstx-(etsz-etyt-grsz+gryt)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{-grz+gtx-zet+zgr}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{\frac{ftr-ft^2x+gstx-etsz+et^2y-gryt}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{gtx-zet}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{\frac{-etsz+et^2y-gry+rztf-xt^2f+txgs}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{t(gx-ze)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{\frac{-t(esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{t(gx-ze)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{\frac{-t(esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} = m^{\frac{t}{et-gr}} n^{\frac{t(gx-ze)}{(et-gr)(rz-tx)}} p^{\frac{t}{rz-tx}},$$

$$b^{esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs} = m^{-(rz-tx)} n^{-(gx-ze)} p^{-(rt-gr)},$$

$$b^{esz-ety-fsr+xtf+gry-xgs} = m^{-(rz-tx)} n^{ez-gx} p^{-(rt-gr)}, \tag{39}$$

Inputting (28), (29), (30), (31), (32), (33), (34), (35), (36), and (37) in (39), I have:

$$b^{\Delta kif} = m^{kif_{12}} n^{kif_{22}} p^{kif_{32}},$$

$$b = m^{\binom{kif_{12}}{\Delta kif}} n^{\binom{kif_{22}}{\Delta kif}} p^{\binom{kif_{32}}{\Delta kif}}, \tag{40}$$

From (17), I have:

$$a^{\frac{e}{f}} b^{\frac{g}{f}} = m^{\frac{1}{f}}, \tag{41}$$

From (18), I have:

$$a^{\frac{r}{s}} b^{\frac{t}{s}} = n^{\frac{1}{s}}, \tag{42}$$

And from (19), I have:

$$a^{\frac{x}{y}} b^{\frac{z}{y}} = p^{\frac{1}{y}}, \tag{43}$$

To eliminate b , divide (41) with (42) and (42) with (43), so we have:

Dividing (41) with (42), so I have

$$a^{\frac{e}{f}} c^{\frac{r}{s}} = m^{\frac{1}{f}} n^{\frac{1}{s}},$$

$$a^{\frac{es-fr}{fs}} c^{\frac{gs-ft}{fs}} = m^{\frac{1}{f}} n^{\frac{1}{s}}, \tag{44}$$

$$ac^{\frac{gs-ft}{es-fr}} = m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{f}{es-fr}}, \tag{45}$$

Dividing (42) with (43), so I have

$$a^{\frac{r}{s}} c^{\frac{t}{y}} = n^{\frac{1}{s}} p^{\frac{1}{y}},$$

$$a^{\frac{ry-sx}{sy}} c^{\frac{ty-sz}{sy}} = n^{\frac{1}{s}} p^{\frac{1}{y}}, \tag{46}$$

$$ac^{\frac{ty-sz}{ry-sx}} = n^{\frac{y}{ry-sx}} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \tag{47}$$

To find c , eliminate a by dividing (45) with (47), so I have:

$$\begin{aligned} c^{\frac{gs-ft}{es-fr} \frac{ty-sz}{ry-sx}} &= m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{f}{es-fr}} \frac{y}{ry-sx} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \\ c^{\frac{(gs-ft)(ry-sx)-(ty-sz)(es-fr)}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} &= m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{-f(ry-sx)-y(es-fr)}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \\ c^{\frac{gsry-gs^2x-ftry+ftsx-(tyes-tyfr-es^2z+szfr)}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} &= m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{-fry+fsx-yes+yfr}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \\ c^{\frac{gsry-gs^2x-ftry+ftsx-tyes+tyfr+es^2z-szfr}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} &= m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{fsx-yes}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \\ c^{\frac{es^2z-tyes+gsry-szfr+ftsx-gs^2x}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} &= m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{s(fx-ye)}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \\ c^{\frac{s(esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs)}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} &= m^{\frac{s}{es-fr}} n^{\frac{s(fx-ye)}{(es-fr)(ry-sx)}} p^{\frac{s}{ry-sx}}, \\ c^{esz-ety+gry-rzf+xtf-xgs} &= m^{ry-sx} n^{fx-ye} p^{es-fr}, \\ c^{esz-ety-fsr+xtf+gry-xgs} &= m^{ry-sx} n^{fx-ye} p^{es-fr}, \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

Inputting (28), (29), (30), (31), (32), (33), (34), (35), (36), and (37) in (48), I have:

$$\begin{aligned} c^{\Delta_{kif}} &= m^{kif_{13}} n^{kif_{23}} p^{kif_{33}}, \\ c &= m^{\left(\frac{kif_{13}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} n^{\left(\frac{kif_{23}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} p^{\left(\frac{kif_{33}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)}, \end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

Generally, Kifilideen’s Rule or model to solve multiplication of tri-indexes simultaneous equations of three variables say a , b and c of the form:

$$\begin{aligned} a^e b^f c^g &= m, \\ a^r b^s c^t &= n, \\ a^x b^y c^z &= p, \end{aligned}$$

is given as:

$$a = m^{\binom{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{31}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$b = m^{\binom{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{32}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$c = m^{\binom{kif_{13}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{23}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{33}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

Generally, Kifilideen's Rule or model to solve multiplication of tetra-indexes simultaneous equations of four variables say a, b, c and d of the form:

$$a^e b^f c^g d^h = m,$$

$$a^r b^s c^t d^j = n,$$

$$a^x b^y c^z d^l = p,$$

$$a^u b^v c^w d^k = q,$$

is given as:

$$a = m^{\binom{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{31}}{\Delta_{kif}}} q^{\binom{kif_{41}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$b = m^{\binom{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{32}}{\Delta_{kif}}} q^{\binom{kif_{42}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$c = m^{\binom{kif_{13}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{23}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{33}}{\Delta_{kif}}} q^{\binom{kif_{43}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$d = m^{\binom{kif_{14}}{\Delta_{kif}}} n^{\binom{kif_{24}}{\Delta_{kif}}} p^{\binom{kif_{34}}{\Delta_{kif}}} q^{\binom{kif_{44}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

3. RESULTS

The Kifilideen's Rule was implemented in form of a model in solving problems involving multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables respectively. The general solution to solve multiplication of n -index simultaneous equations of n variables using Kifilideen's rule was inaugurated.

3.1. Implementation of the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables

1. Solve the multiplication of bi-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables using Kifilideen's Rule given that:

$$x^5 y^2 = 288, \quad (50)$$

$$x^3 y^4 = 648, \quad (51)$$

Solution

The Δ_{kif} = the determinant of matrix of the input index system

$$\Delta_{kif} = \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 2 \\ 3 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 20 - 6, \quad \Delta_{kif} = 14,$$

kif = the matrix of the input index system

$$kif = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 2 \\ 3 & 4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix},$$

The components of the cofactor of kif are given as:

$$kif_{11} = \text{cofactor of } a_{11} = 4,$$

$$kif_{12} = \text{cofactor of } a_{12} = -3,$$

$$kif_{21} = \text{cofactor of } a_{21} = -2,$$

$$kif_{22} = \text{cofactor of } a_{22} = 5,$$

Using Kifilideen's Rule, I have:

$$x = m \left(\frac{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}} \right) n \left(\frac{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}} \right),$$

$$x = 288 \left(\frac{4}{14} \right) 648 \left(\frac{-2}{14} \right),$$

$$x = (288^4 648^{-2})^{\frac{1}{14}},$$

$$x = (16384)^{\frac{1}{14}},$$

$$x = 2,$$

$$y = m \left(\frac{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}} \right) n \left(\frac{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}} \right),$$

$$y = (288^{-3} 648^5)^{\frac{1}{14}},$$

$$y = (4782969)^{\frac{1}{14}},$$

$$y = 3,$$

$$\text{So, } x = 2 \text{ and } y = 3.$$

The implementation of the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables is short, effective, accurate and easy to understand and comprehend. It can also be applied if the indexes are negative values.

3.2. Utilization of the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of tri-indexes simultaneous equations of three variables

2. Solve the multiplication of trii-indexes simultaneous equations of three variables using Kifilideen's Rule given that:

$$r^3s^4t^2 = 18,000, \quad (52)$$

$$r^1s^5t^6 = 116,640, \quad (53)$$

$$r^2s^3t^1 = 600, \quad (54)$$

Solution

The Δ_{kif} = the determinant of matrix of the input index system

$$\Delta_{kif} = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 4 & 2 \\ 1 & 5 & 6 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 3 \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 6 \\ 3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} - 4 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 6 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} + 2 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 \\ 2 & 3 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 3(5 - 18) - 4(1 - 12) + 2(3 - 10),$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 3(-13) - 4(-11) + 2(-7),$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = -39 + 44 - 14,$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = -9,$$

kif = the matrix of the input index system

$$kif = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 4 & 2 \\ 1 & 5 & 6 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

The components of the cofactor of kif are given as:

$$kif_{11} = \text{cofactor of } a_{11} = \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 6 \\ 3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 5 - 18 = -13,$$

$$kif_{12} = \text{cofactor of } a_{12} = - \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 6 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = -(1 - 12) = 11,$$

$$kif_{13} = \text{cofactor of } a_{13} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 \\ 2 & 3 \end{vmatrix} = 3 - 10 = -7,$$

$$kif_{21} = \text{cofactor of } a_{21} = - \begin{vmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = -(4 - 6) = 2,$$

$$kif_{22} = \text{cofactor of } a_{22} = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 2 \\ 2 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 3 - 4 = -1,$$

$$kif_{23} = \text{cofactor of } a_{23} = - \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 4 \\ 2 & 3 \end{vmatrix} = -(9 - 8) = -1,$$

$$kif_{31} = \text{cofactor of } a_{31} = \begin{vmatrix} 4 & 2 \\ 5 & 6 \end{vmatrix} = 24 - 10 = 14,$$

$$kif_{32} = \text{cofactor of } a_{32} = - \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 2 \\ 1 & 6 \end{vmatrix} = -(18 - 2) = -16,$$

$$kif_{33} = \text{cofactor of } a_{33} = \begin{vmatrix} 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 5 \end{vmatrix} = 15 - 4 = 11,$$

Using Kifilideen's Rule, I have:

$$r = m \binom{kif_{11}}{\Delta kif} n \binom{kif_{21}}{\Delta kif} p \binom{kif_{31}}{\Delta kif},$$

$$r = (18,000^{-13} \times 116,640^2 \times 600^{14})^{\frac{-1}{9}},$$

$$r = (18,000^{13} \times 116,640^{-2} \times 600^{-14})^{\frac{1}{9}},$$

$$r = (1953125)^{\frac{1}{9}},$$

$$r = 5,$$

$$s = m \binom{kif_{12}}{\Delta kif} n \binom{kif_{22}}{\Delta kif} p \binom{kif_{32}}{\Delta kif},$$

$$s = (18,000^{11} \times 116,640^{-1} \times 600^{-16})^{\frac{-1}{9}},$$

$$s = (18,000^{-11} \times 116,640^1 \times 600^{16})^{\frac{1}{9}},$$

$$s = (512)^{\frac{1}{9}},$$

$$s = 2,$$

$$t = m \binom{kif_{13}}{\Delta kif} n \binom{kif_{23}}{\Delta kif} p \binom{kif_{33}}{\Delta kif},$$

$$t = (18,000^{-7} \times 116,640^{-1} \times 600^{11})^{\frac{-1}{9}},$$

$$t = (18,000^7 \times 116,640^1 \times 600^{-11})^{\frac{1}{9}},$$

$$t = (18683)^{\frac{1}{9}},$$

$$t = 3,$$

So, $r = 5$, $s = 2$ and $t = 3$.

The utilization of the Kifilideen's Rule or Model to solve multiplication of tri-indexes simultaneous equations of three variables indicates that the model is simple, accurate, interesting, straightforward, easy and initiative to understand, short and effective. It can also be applied if the indexes are negative values.

3.3. Significance of Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes and n -index simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables and n variables respectively

The Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes and n -index simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables and n variables respectively as significance and importance in the area of population growth analysis, forecasting, finance, chemistry, agriculture, biology, computer science, physics, engineering, industry, manufacturing

company and game design. The Kifilideen's Rule can be applied in the population growth that follows geometric growth of factor or change in factors of multiplier over time.

For example, three bacteria of population, P_0 increase by a factor of x each for n times for first bacteria, m times for second bacteria and v times for third bacteria respectively and later on the population of the three bacteria start to increase by a factor of y each for u times for first bacteria, p times for second bacteria and q times for third bacteria respectively. At the end of the u times, p times and q times multiplication of the population of the three bacteria respectively, the total populations of the three bacteria are P_1 , P_2 and P_3 respectively. The mathematical equations of this scenario are given as:

$$\begin{aligned} P_1 &= P_0 x^n y^u, \\ P_2 &= P_0 x^m y^p \text{ and} \\ P_3 &= P_0 x^v y^q. \end{aligned}$$

The Kifilideen's Rule can be used to solve for the values of factors of x and y of the growth of the population of the bacteria and also the initial population of the bacteria in a simplify way with exact value been generated.

More so, the Kifilideen's Rule can be applied in a system which grow geometrically where the value of a physical quantity e.g. cost of good of the system increases with a factor at a level for a particular number of times and as the physical quantity migrate to higher level, the values of the physical quantity multiply with increase by another factor for a particular number of times where the resulting total geometric process produce a value. The Kifilideen's Rule can be used to determine the value of the factors at which the physical quantity is increasing for each level and also the initial value of the physical quantity before geometric growth can be known using the rule. Furthermore, the Kifilideen's Rule can be used to solve geometric sequence problem of the form

$$T_n = ar^{n-1}$$

Where, a is the first term and r is the common ratio which lead to simultaneous equations of multiplication of two-indexes of two variables (Xin et al., 2018; Liao et al., 2022). The Kifilideen's Rule is used to find the value of the first term, a and the common ratio, r .

The Kifilideen's Rule can be applied in industries where products are designed into different sizes of levels and steps where within levels the size of the product is increasing with a factor and across the levels the size of the product is increasing with another factor. The values of the common ratios within and across the levels of the structural framework can be obtained using

the Kifilideen's Rule. Also, the initial size of the product before change in size within and across the levels can be attained utilizing the Kifilideen's Rule.

In salary structure, that follows geometric sequence, Kifilideen's Rule can be applied in determining the components values of the system of that salary structure. The significance of the Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes and n -indexes simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables and n variables respectively are the provision of a systematic and structural way to approach and solve problem in a precise and accurate manner to produce values of the solution of the variables and help to streamline problem solving processes of the simultaneous equations. The application of the Kifilideen's Rule enables predications and forecasting. The rule helps to simplify the solution from complex problem to easier solution. Furthermore, the Kifilideen's Rule helps to fosters critical thinking, analytical skills and would enhances cognitive skill when fully utilize. More so, the rule provides a logical framework for the analysis of the variables of a system. The rule speed up the problem-solving process, as its avoids the need for trial and error or unnecessary calculation, enhancing both efficiency and accuracy. The Kifilideen's Rule is a powerful tool for problem-solving across various scenarios.

3.4.Application of Kifilideen's Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables respectively

(1) Three bacteria of population, P_0 increase by a factor of x each for 5 times for first bacteria, 2 times for second bacteria and 4 times for third bacteria respectively and later on the population of the three bacteria start to increase by a factor of y each for 3 times for first bacteria, 6 times for second bacteria and 2 times for third bacteria respectively. At the end of the 3 times, 6 times and 2 times multiplication of the population of the three bacteria respectively, the total populations of the three bacteria are $P_1 = 432,000$, $P_2 = 1,458,000$ and $P_3 = 72,000$ respectively. Determine

- (i) initial population, P_0 of each of the bacteria,
- (ii) the factors, x of the population growth,
- (iii) the factors, y of the population growth.

Solution

The mathematical equations of the population growth of the three bacteria are given as:

$$P_1 = P_0 x^5 y^3 = 432,000,$$

$$P_2 = P_0 x^2 y^6 = 1,458,000 \text{ and}$$

$$P_3 = P_0 x^4 y^2 = 72,000.$$

The Δ_{kif} = the determinant of matrix of the input index system

$$\Delta_{kif} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 6 \\ 1 & 4 & 2 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 1 \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 6 \\ 4 & 2 \end{vmatrix} - 5 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 6 \\ 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} + 3 \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 4 \end{vmatrix}$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 1(4 - 24) - 5(2 - 6) + 3(4 - 2),$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 1(-20) - 5(-4) + 3(2),$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = -20 + 20 + 6,$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 6,$$

kif = the matrix of the input index system

$$kif = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 5 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 6 \\ 1 & 4 & 2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{31} & a_{32} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}$$

The components of the cofactor of kif are given as:

$$kif_{11} = \text{cofactor of } a_{11} = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 6 \\ 4 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 24 = -20,$$

$$kif_{12} = \text{cofactor of } a_{12} = - \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 6 \\ 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = -(2 - 6) = 4,$$

$$kif_{13} = \text{cofactor of } a_{13} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 2 \\ 1 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = 4 - 2 = 2,$$

$$kif_{21} = \text{cofactor of } a_{21} = - \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 3 \\ 4 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = -(10 - 12) = 2,$$

$$kif_{22} = \text{cofactor of } a_{22} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 2 - 3 = -1,$$

$$kif_{23} = \text{cofactor of } a_{23} = - \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 \\ 1 & 4 \end{vmatrix} = -(4 - 5) = 1,$$

$$kif_{31} = \text{cofactor of } a_{31} = \begin{vmatrix} 5 & 3 \\ 2 & 6 \end{vmatrix} = 30 - 6 = 24,$$

$$kif_{32} = \text{cofactor of } a_{32} = - \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 3 \\ 1 & 6 \end{vmatrix} = -(6 - 3) = -3,$$

$$kif_{33} = \text{cofactor of } a_{33} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 5 \\ 1 & 2 \end{vmatrix} = 2 - 5 = -3,$$

Using Kifilideen's Rule, I have:

$$P_o = (432,000) \binom{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}} (1,458,000) \binom{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}} (72,000) \binom{kif_{31}}{\Delta_{kif}},$$

$$P_o = (432,000) \binom{-20}{6} (1,458,000) \binom{2}{6} (72,000) \binom{24}{6},$$

$$P_o = ((432,000)^{-20} (1,458,000)^2 (72,000)^{24}) \frac{1}{6},$$

$$P_o = (1.5625 \times 10^{16})^{\frac{1}{6}},$$

P_o = initial population of each of the bacteria = 500,

$$x = (432,000)^{\left(\frac{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} (1,458,000)^{\left(\frac{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} (72,000)^{\left(\frac{kif_{32}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)},$$

$$x = (432,000)^{\left(\frac{4}{6}\right)} (1,458,000)^{\left(\frac{-1}{6}\right)} (72,000)^{\left(\frac{-3}{6}\right)},$$

$$x = ((432,000)^4 (1,458,000)^{-1} (72,000)^{-3})^{\frac{1}{6}},$$

$$x = (64)^{\frac{1}{6}},$$

$$x = 2$$

The factors, x of the population growth = 2

$$y = (432,000)^{\left(\frac{kif_{13}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} (1,458,000)^{\left(\frac{kif_{23}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)} (72,000)^{\left(\frac{kif_{33}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)},$$

$$y = (432,000)^{\left(\frac{2}{6}\right)} (1,458,000)^{\left(\frac{1}{6}\right)} (72,000)^{\left(\frac{-3}{6}\right)},$$

$$y = ((432,000)^2 (1,458,000)^1 (72,000)^{-3})^{\frac{1}{6}},$$

$$y = (729)^{\frac{1}{6}},$$

$$y = 3$$

The factors, y of the population growth = 3

(2) The initial salary of a staff in an organization is ₦ a . If the salary of the staff is increasing geometrically as the staff migrates from his initial organization to higher organizations due to the complexity of the nature of work carry out by the staff in the higher organizations. After the increase in salary of the staff by a factor of u for 4 times as the staff migrates to higher organizations, the staff is receiving ₦480,000. If after the increase in salary of the staff by a factor of u for 7 times as the staff migrates to higher organizations, the staff is receiving ₦3,840,000.

Determine the

- (i) the initial salary of the staff, ₦ a in the first organization,
- (ii) the factor, u , at which the salary of the staff is increasing.

Solution

The mathematical equations of the salary growth of staff are given as:

$$au^4 = \text{₦}480,000,$$

$$au^7 = \text{₦}3,840,000,$$

The Δ_{kif} = the determinant of matrix of the input index system

$$\Delta_{kif} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 4 \\ 1 & 7 \end{vmatrix} = 7 - 4,$$

$$\Delta_{kif} = 3,$$

kif =the matrix of the input index system

$$kif = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 4 \\ 1 & 7 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix},$$

The components of the cofactor of kif are given as:

$$kif_{11} = \text{cofactor of } a_{11} = 7,$$

$$kif_{12} = \text{cofactor of } a_{12} = -1,$$

$$kif_{21} = \text{cofactor of } a_{21} = -4,$$

$$kif_{22} = \text{cofactor of } a_{22} = 1,$$

Using Kifilideen’s Rule, I have:

$$\mathbb{N}a = (480,000)^{\binom{kif_{11}}{\Delta_{kif}}} (3,840,000)^{\binom{kif_{21}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$\mathbb{N}a = (480,000)^{\binom{7}{3}} (3,840,000)^{\binom{-4}{3}}$$

$$\mathbb{N}a = ((480,000)^7 (3,840,000)^{-4})^{\frac{1}{3}},$$

$$\mathbb{N}a = (2.7 \times 10^{13})^{\frac{1}{3}},$$

$$\mathbb{N}a = \mathbb{N}30,000,$$

The initial salary of the staff, $\mathbb{N}a$ in the first organization= $\mathbb{N}30,000$

$$u = (480,000)^{\binom{kif_{12}}{\Delta_{kif}}} (3,840,000)^{\binom{kif_{22}}{\Delta_{kif}}},$$

$$u = (480,000)^{\binom{-1}{3}} (3,840,000)^{\binom{1}{3}}$$

$$u = ((480,000)^{-1} (3,840,000)^1)^{\frac{1}{3}},$$

$$u = (8)^{\frac{1}{3}},$$

$$u = 2,$$

The factor, u , at which the salary of the staff is increasing= 2

Let us give the following theorem without proof

Theorem. Let the following equation be the system.

$$\prod_{i=1}^n x_{1i}^{t_{1i}} = b_1,$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^n x_{1i}^{t_{2i}} = b_2, \text{ where } n \in \mathbb{Z}^+$$

$$\prod_{i=1}^n x_{1i}^{t_{ni}} = b_n.$$

If the solution of the system of equations has only one solution, then

$$x_{11} = \prod_{i=1}^n b_i^{\left(\frac{kif_{i1}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)},$$

$$x_{12} = \prod_{i=1}^n b_i^{\left(\frac{kif_{i2}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)},$$

·
·

$$x_{1n} = \prod_{i=1}^n b_i^{\left(\frac{kif_{in}}{\Delta_{kif}}\right)}.$$

4. CONCLUSION

This study develops Kifilideen’s Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes, tri-indexes and n -index simultaneous equations of two variables, three variables and n variables respectively. Elimination method, laws of indices, and cofactor and determinant of matrix were deployed in establishing, formulating and modeling the Kifilideen’s Rule to solve multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables respectively. The Kifilideen’s Rule was implemented in form of a model in solving problems involving multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables respectively. The general solution to solve multiplication of n -index simultaneous equations of n variables using Kifilideen’s rule was inaugurated. The Kifilideen’s Rule is in form of a model to solve multiplication of bi-indexes and tri-indexes simultaneous equations of two variables and three variables respectively which was found to be effective, straightforward, reliable, interesting, easy and initiative to understand for students and beginners. The general solution for n to this rule is transferred to the discussion.

5. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to express heartfelt gratitude to Allah for His mercy, guidance, and the wisdom granted to complete this work. The author also acknowledges the opportunity to contribute this mathematical invention to the scientific community under the auspices of the Momona Ethiopian Journal of Science.

7. REFERENCE

- Baki, A. 1992. Al Khwarizmi's Contributions to the Science of Mathematics: Al Kitab Al Jabr Wa'l Muqabalah. *Journal of Islamic Academy of Sciences*, **5(3)**: 225-228, https://jag.journalagent.com/ias/pdfs/IAS_5_3_225_228.pdf
- Burton, D. M. 2011. *The History of Mathematics: An Introduction*. McGraw-Hill, Inc., 819p, <https://jontalle.web.engr.illinois.edu/uploads/298/HistoryMath-Burton.85.pdf>
- Carmine, B. 2021. Mathematics: Innovation and Progress. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering and Management Research*, **6 (4)**: 12-23, https://www.ijaemr.com/uploads/pdf/archivepdf/2021/IJAEMR_458.pdf
- Fribera, J. 2008. A Remarkable Collection of Babylonian Mathematical Texts. *Notices of the AMS*, **55 (9)**: 1076-1086, <https://www.ams.org/notices/200809/tx080901076p.pdf>
- Grcar, J. F. 2011a. Mathematicians of Gaussian Elimination. *Notices of the AMS*, **58 (6)**:782-792, <https://www.cis.upenn.edu/~cis6100/Notices-06-11-Gausselim.pdf>
- Grcar, J. F. 2011b. How Ordinary Elimination Became Gaussian Elimination. *Historia Mathematica*, **38**: 163-218, <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.hm.2010.06.003>.
- Heffer, A & Rothman, T. 2014. On Remembering Cardano Anew. *The Mathematical Intelligencer*, 1-15, <http://doi.org/10.1007/s00283-014-9444-6>
- Kabar, M. G. D. 2023. A Thematic Review of Quadratic Equation Studies in the Field of Mathematics Education. *Participatory Educational Research (PER)*, **10(4)**: 29-48, <http://dx.doi.org/10.17275/per.23.58.10.4>
- Khushbu, K & Poonia, R. K. 2021. A Study of Solving System of Linear Equation using Different Methods and its Real-Life Applications. *Journal of University of Shanghai for Science and Technology*, **23 (7)**: 723-733, <https://jusst.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/A-STUDY-OF-SOLVING-SYSTEM-OF-LINEAR-EQUATION-USING-DIFFERENT-METHODS-AND-ITS-REAL-LIFE-APPLICATIONS.pdf>

- Liao, T.F., Bolano, D., Brzinsky-Fay, C., Cornwell, B., Fasang, A.E., Helske, S., Piccarreta, R., Raab, M., Ritschard, G., Struffolino, E & Studer, M. 2022. Sequence analysis: its past, present and future. *Social Science Research*, **107**: 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssresearch.2022.102772>.
- Neovius, S. 2013. René Descartes' Foundations of Analytic Geometry and Classification of Curves. U.U.D.M. Project Report Uppsala Universitet, Sweden, 30p, <https://uu.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:631055/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Oaks, J. A. 2021. Fermat and Descartes in Light of Premodern Algebra and Vi`ete. In: Sriraman B. (eds) Handbook of the History and Philosophy of Mathematical Practice. Springer, Cham, 134p, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19071-2_8-1.
- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2020a. Development of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem Using Matrix Approach. *International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology*, **7 (7)**: 117- 135, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5794742>.
- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2020b. Utilization of Kifilideen Trinomial based on Matrix Approach in Computation of the Power of Base of Tri-Digits Number. International Conference on Electrical Engineering Applications (ICEEA 2020), Department of Electrical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria. September 23-25, 2020, pp. 192 – 199, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5794756>.
- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2021. Inauguration of Negative Power of – of Kifilideen Trinomial Theorem using Standardized and Matrix Methods. *Acta Electronica Malaysia (AEM)*, **5 (1)**: 17 – 23, <http://doi.org/10.26480/aem.01.2021.17.23>.
- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2022. Derivation of Formulas of the Components of Kifilideen Trinomial Expansion of Positive Power of N with Other Developments. *Journal of Science, Technology, Mathematics and Education (JOSTMED)*, **18 (1)**: 1 – 21, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12596950>.
- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2023. Generation of Kifilideen's Generalized Matrix Progression Sequence of Infinite Term. *Ethiopian Journal of Science and Sustainable Development*, **10 (2)**: 74-99, <https://doi.org/10.20372/ejssdastu:v10.i2.2023.710>.
- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2024a. Development of Kifilideen's Elimination Matrix Model to Solve Simultaneous Equations of Four Variables (w, x, y, and z), Three Variables (x, y, and z), and Two Variables (x and y). *Noumerico: Journal of Technology in Mathematics Education*, **2(2)**: 127-155, <https://doi.org/10.33367/jtme.v2i2.5352>.

- Osanyinpeju, K. L. 2024b. Development and Applications of Finite Term of Kifilideen's Generalized Matrix Progression Sequence in Actual Life. *East African Journal of Sciences*, **18 (2)**: 181-204, <https://doi.org/10.20372/eajs.v18i2.2155>.
- Rahaman, M. L. 2022. Contribution of Arabs in Mathematics in Middle Ages. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, **10 (2)**: 534-542, <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2202069.pdf>
- Rizos, I & Gkrekas, N. 2022. The Historical Background of a Famous Indeterminate Problem and Some Teaching Perspectives. *Journal of Mathematics and Statistics Studies*, 1-8, <http://doi.org/10.32996/jmss.2022.3.1>.
- Samuel, U. O. 2012. Students' Preference of Method of Solving Simultaneous Equations. *Global Journal of Educational Research*, **11 (2)**: 129 – 136, <http://dx.doi.org/10.4314/gjedr.v11i2.8>.
- Sfard, A. 1995. The Development of Algebra: Confronting Historical and Psychological Perspectives. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, **14**: 15–39, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0732-3123\(95\)90022-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0732-3123(95)90022-5).
- Woollard, L. 2015. Planning for progression- the debate around the use of the elimination method in the teaching of simultaneous equations. *The STeP Journal*, **2(2)**: 88-97, <https://ojs.cumbria.ac.uk/stepPDF>.
- Xin, G., Zhang, J & Wei, Z. 2018. Deep leaning for sequence pattern recognition. Conference: 2018 IEEE 15th International Conference on Networking, Sensing and Control (ICNSC), 7p, <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICNSC.2018.8361281>.
- Zara, T. 2008. A Brief Study of Some Aspects of Babylonian Mathematics. A Senior Thesis Liberty University, 36p, <https://math.hawaii.edu/~mchyba/documents/syllabus/Math499/Babylonians/Babylonian.pdf>.